

Clinical Parameters

Sno	ID	Age	Gender (M/F)	Data acquired for Raman	Data acquired for ATR-FTIR	Mass Spectrometry
1	Acromegaly 0001	28	M	Yes	Yes	NA
2	Acromegaly 53	29	F	Yes	Yes	NA
3	Acromegaly 68	40	M	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	Acromegaly 73	44	M	Yes	NA	NA
5	Acromegaly 76	41	F	Yes	Yes	NA
6	Acromegaly 100	45	F	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	Acromegaly 145	45	F	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	Acromegaly 149	32	F	NA	Yes	NA
9	Acromegaly 155	48	F	Yes	Yes	NA
10	Acromegaly 157	25	F	NA	Yes	Yes
11	Acromegaly 161	50	F	Yes	Yes	Yes
12	Acromegaly 183	65	F	Yes	NA	NA
13	Acromegaly 189	48	M	NA	Yes	NA
14	Acromegaly 211	34	M	NA	Yes	NA
15	Acromegaly 214	54	F	Yes	NA	NA
16	Acromegaly 239	55	F	Yes	Yes	Yes
17	Acromegaly 267	34	F	Yes	Yes	NA
18	Acromegaly 269	44	F	Yes	Yes	NA
19	Acromegaly 273	35	F	Yes	NA	NA
20	Acromegaly 274	23	M	Yes	Yes	NA
21	Acromegaly 282	40	M	NA	NA	Yes
22	Acromegaly 285	38	F	NA	NA	Yes
23	Cushing's 25	21	F	Yes	NA	NA
24	Cushing's 75	24	M	Yes	Yes	NA
25	Cushing's 114	22	M	Yes	Yes	NA
26	Cushing's 129	21	F	NA	Yes	NA
27	Cushing's 141	25	M	Yes	NA	NA
28	Cushing's 149	32	F	Yes	NA	NA
29	Cushing's 150	18	M	Yes	Yes	NA
30	Cushing's 163	55	F	Yes	Yes	NA
31	Cushing's 165	36	F	NA	Yes	NA
32	Cushing's 181	39	F	Yes	Yes	Yes
33	Cushing's 185	18	F	Yes	Yes	Yes
34	Cushing's 195	22	M	Yes	Yes	Yes
35	Cushing's 198	50	F	Yes	Yes	Yes
36	Cushing's 199	18	F	Yes	Yes	NA
37	Cushing's 209	62	F	Yes	Yes	NA
38	Cushing's 211	34	M	Yes	Yes	NA
39	Cushing's 213	28	M	Yes	Yes	NA
40	Cushing's 224	25	M	NA	Yes	Yes
41	Cushing's 247	41	F	Yes	Yes	Yes

42	Cushing's 248	18	M	Yes	NA	Yes
43	Cushing's 256	38	F	Yes	NA	NA
44	Cushing's 257	46	M	Yes	Yes	Yes
45	Cushing's 265	30	F	NA	Yes	NA
46	NFPA 26	58	M	Yes	NA	NA
47	NFPA 33	42	F	NA	Yes	NA
48	NFPA 49	65	F	Yes	NA	NA
49	NFPA 58	42	F	Yes	Yes	NA
50	NFPA 79	40	M	Yes	Yes	Yes
51	NFPA 84	42	F	Yes	NA	NA
52	NFPA 96	56	F	Yes	Yes	Yes
53	NFPA 105	45	F	Yes	NA	NA
54	NFPA 106	65	M	Yes	Yes	NA
55	NFPA 115	47	F	Yes	NA	NA
56	NFPA 130	50	F	Yes	NA	NA
57	NFPA 132	40	F	Yes	Yes	NA
58	NFPA 138	58	F	Yes	Yes	Yes
59	NFPA 148	50	M	Yes	Yes	NA
60	NFPA 152	38	M	Yes	NA	NA
61	NFPA 160	47	M	Yes	NA	NA
62	NFPA 164	45	M	Yes	Yes	NA
63	NFPA 178	26	M	Yes	Yes	Yes
64	NFPA 179	53	M	Yes	NA	NA
65	NFPA 184	30	F	Yes	NA	NA
66	NFPA 188	30	M	Yes	Yes	Yes
67	NFPA 190	48	M	Yes	Yes	Yes
68	NFPA 204	18	M	Yes	NA	NA
69	NFPA 208	55	M	Yes	NA	NA
70	NFPA 218	20	F	Yes	Yes	NA
71	NFPA 219	68	M	Yes	Yes	Yes
72	NFPA 221	60	M	Yes	Yes	NA
73	NFPA 230	30	M	Yes	Yes	NA
74	NFPA 242	22	M	Yes	NA	NA
75	NFPA 243	33	M	Yes	Yes	Yes
76	NFPA 246	54	F	Yes	Yes	NA
77	NFPA 249	55	M	Yes	Yes	NA
78	NFPA 252	68	M	Yes	Yes	Yes
79	NFPA 263	54	M	Yes	NA	NA
80	NFPA 270	55	M	NA	Yes	NA
81	NFPA 271	65	M	NA	Yes	NA
82	Control 1	42	M	Yes	Yes	NA
83	Control 2	50	M	Yes	Yes	NA
84	Control 3	35	M	Yes	Yes	NA
85	Control 4	32	M	Yes	Yes	NA
86	Control 5	38	M	Yes	Yes	NA

87	Control 6	22	M	Yes	Yes	NA
88	Control 7	35	M	Yes	Yes	NA
89	Control 8	30	M	Yes	Yes	NA